

Tort liabilities

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Abstract: Consideration of obligations arising out of damage caused to identities or the property of individuals, theme analysis.

Key words: cause of damage, property damage, moral damage, restitution, obligations, civic legislation.

In the course of identities' interactions, organizations of other subjects of civic rights, the damage can be caused to their property and personal non-material benefits. It can happen accidentally, by purpose, negligence or due to the reaction of irresistible force of nature. When damage is caused there is the necessity to determine who is to bear its consequences: the victim, the person who caused the damage, or the third person who is neither the victim, nor the committer of the tort.

Usually consequences of the caused damage can not be eliminated or compensated with the aid of any lawful institute. To achieve maximum social effect the so called tort obligations are used as well as other lawful means.

Civic legislation regulates property and personal non-property relationships and their participants connected to it.

Civic rights arise out of the principles, specified by the law or other law acts, for example:

- out of contracts, deals, which are stipulated by the law;
- as a result of property acquisition ;
- due to the damage caused to another identity etc.

Most obligations arise out of acts of lawful, permitted or useful activity such as acts of planning, contracts or one side deals. Another thing is referred to security obligations, arising outside contractual relationships due to the damage caused, rescue of property, groundless acquisition of property or saving property.

In case one individual causes property damage to another one, it often happens in connection with unlawful actions. It is also illegal acquisition or saving property by one individual at the expenses of another one without any grounds to do it. However under certain circumstances unlawful actions cause civic lawful obligation to compensate for property damage or return the property which is groundlessly acquired. Obligations of such kind have the dual purpose.

Firstly, they serve to secure state and personal property i.e. threat of property sanctions play the preventive role, it prevents from causing damage to the state and individual's property, as well as other legal and obligation factors prevent it. But if despite to preventive measures the property damage is anyway done, it's compensation at the expenses of a lawbreaker will ensure the restoration of the owner's status which had been at the moment when damage was done or when another person had acquired the property at his expenses.

Secondly, obligations arising out of the caused damage also serve to defend interests of the identity, it's life and health.

The damage caused to identity can also cause property losses in the form of medical expenses or loss of wages due to loss of earning capacity. Civic responsibility for such damage is sufficient because it fulfils the preventive and compensation functions.

Health protection right is one of the main points of the lawful status of identity.

According to the Constitution all citizens have the right to health protection. Society, state is also interested to protect life, health and earning capacity of citizens - active entrepreneurs, one of the main tasks of which is the complete satisfaction of all identity's demands.

The government underlines the creation of the most favourable conditions for businessmen, private firms, support of small business, introduction of more modern equipment as the main direction in the sphere of social development. So, the problem of protection of environment and improvement of man's health is one of the principal purposes of the developed society.

Principles of labour legislation strengthen one of the main rights of workers and servants-the right to health and labour safety, guarantee of which is laid upon company's administration, establishments and organizations. Administration is to introduce modern means of safety to prevent industrial traumas, to stop workmen's professional diseases.

The main role in protection of material interests of individuals who lost earning capacity or lost a bread winner belongs to the civic rights, including the norms, regulating obligations, arising out of the damage caused to the identity, directed to the prevention of accidents and to compensate for the damage done to health.

Damage caused to the identity or individual's property is subjected to compensation in whole by the person who caused the damage. The law says about the identity or the individual's property, however the character of the damage is determined not by the direct object of the damage attempt, but by the results of the damage, depending on what extent lawbreaker's illegal actions effected the property's condition or moral status of identity who incurred the damage. Very often the result of life attempt is the loss of earning capacity and accordingly reduction or loss of wages. This is a property damage. However, as a rule damage to health is accompanied with the physical damage, and to the extent that causes victim's moral pains – is the moral damage.

Legislation stipulates restitution, because the victim of damage is interested in liquidation of all unfavorable consequences both material and moral, caused by illegal offender's conduct. Tort liabilities are directed to restore victim's property status in that form in which it were before in the event the damage would not have been done.

However, sometimes when the damage to health is done or it brought to individual's death the moral losses can not be compensated. So, as a rule if the restitution satisfy owner's needs, even the full restoration of the material status of the person who lost earning capacity is not able to satisfy his moral demands. That is why the meaning of restitution is not limited by the compensation, recovery functions. [2 page 48]

So it's more important to prevent health damage and damage caused to individual. Based on this, social meaning of lawful regulations of restitution relationships is that they must also be directed to provide educational and preventive functions.

In most cases the damage done to employees occurs at the fault of the employer, such facts as failure to guarantee healthy conditions and safety, failure to comply with occupational safety regulations, industrial hygiene and so on witness it.

This is the confirmation that employers must introduce educational and preventive functions in order to avoid damages.

Presently some changes in economics, increase of companies with the private form of property, development of business activity, introduction of new modern equipment in industry take place, and also new relationships in use of labour appear.

A lot of problems related to restitution which demand proper constructive decisions appear during the transitional and crisis period in the countries with unstable economics.

I'd like to note that in connection with rise of civilization, prompt development of physiological and intellectual skills, responsibility for the damage done by teenagers start from 14 years old.

Earlier the restitution was based on the law, on labour code and that was all, nowadays except for the law, contractual obligations are stipulated. The old legislation did not stipulate the moral damage.

Presently this issue is confirmed in the articles 951,952 of the Civic code of the RoK.

Moral damage is compensated irrespective of whether the material damage is done or not.

Then later principles of the Civic Code of the USSR and the republic were used in the Civic code of the RoK that involved clear and more concrete presentation of articles and widening of the normative legislation that improved it's use.

The main issue is to prevent damage.

In order to prevent it, it is necessary to conduct a general, elementary tuition at school and also conduct tuition for adults in the industry, to conduct explanation work in Press, radio and TV.

It may reduce appearing of tort commission among the population, but however whilst there is no material basis and the country's economics is unstable, there will be quite a lot of committers of tort.

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